

Shockwaves and Meaning in Quantum Theory

Exploring the dynamics of a simple fluid system to determine the requirements for a unified model of physics

Introduction

Quantum mechanics interpretations like Bohmian mechanics that arise from fluid dynamics are not widely accepted due to several unresolved issues. The goal of this project is to present a simplified fluid model that could address these issues. That model produces interactions similar to the standard model with particle analogues that emerge from shockwave interactions. This could provide a consistent physical description of quantum behavior and clarify several confusing aspects of quantum theory. If correct, it suggests a new hydrodynamic interpretation of quantum mechanics and supports recent proposals that suggest gravity emerges from entanglement or entropy.

After briefly discussing the origin of this model we will review the issues raised with Bohmian mechanics and similar interpretations. We will then take a standard fluid model and make modifications to attempt addressing those issues. Next we will attempt to duplicate the interactions of the standard model with various fluid dynamics. I am not finished with this work yet, and I have only vague ideas about some features. I will describe the dynamics of the model as I understand it and how I think they produce standard model-like behavior. After that we will discuss what this interpretation suggests about a unified model of physics.

Motivation

This model did not arise from investigating hydrodynamic interpretations or fluid dynamics, but from QCD. I was attempting to improve my layman's understanding of quantum chromodynamics and the color charge. The visualization I came to was to think of the color charge as directional; a vector of force that must be countered for the particle to exist. Thus color confinement would mean that the momentum of a composite particle does not include the part of a quark's momentum negated by color charge. Although I found descriptions of color charge as a vector, I did not find anyone using this comparison.

It occurred to me that if you modeled a quark as rotated toward a compactified dimension representing color charge you could model the electric charge as partially negated in addition to the momentum, representing the fractional charge of quarks. This led to the creation of several toy models, but I eventually concluded that the same dynamics could be produced by the fluid model described below. I believe that the behavior of this fluid reproduces the interactions of the standard model. The physical description of quantum behavior it suggests is, as far as I'm aware, a unique interpretation.

As I am neither a physicist nor a mathematician I will not claim this model is defined rigorously and I'll leave questions of its validity to more experienced readers. Similarly, while I can demonstrate behavior like the standard model I have no evidence this represents reality and I do not have the expertise to determine if it is mathematically equivalent. I am only claiming this model is a reasonable approximation of fluid behavior and can also show a reasonable approximation of the standard model. I believe this is an interpretation of quantum systems that provides new clarity. Indeed, I suspect that the fluid model proposed here is only a simplification of the math of quantum field theory which I have not studied. (The difference between a fluid and a field escapes me, as fluid dynamics is described by a velocity field. As this work represents a deterministic field and not a quantum field, I will still refer to the model as a fluid.) Whether this model is only a useful metaphor or a valid physical representation is beyond my ability to determine.

Constraints on Fluid Interpretations

The first and most well known hydrodynamic interpretation is pilot wave theory, or Bohmian mechanics. This postulates a physical particle whose path is determined by guiding waves. Since it models probabilistic quantum behavior with classical deterministic physics, like other fluid interpretations it is a hidden variable interpretation. That is, it suggests that the probabilities of quantum mechanics arise from the statistics of untracked variables. The issues with hidden variable theories presented below are mostly adapted from David Wallace's 2007 review of the measurement problem, which presents various quantum interpretations and their challenges (arXiv:0712.0149).

Many claim that the Bell inequality proves hidden variable theories cannot be valid. This is not actually correct. In fact, Bell himself was a supporter of Bohmian mechanics. What Bell's theorem shows is that hidden variable interpretations must be non local; that is they must have features that propagate instantaneously. Bohmian mechanics postulates a guiding wave that is influenced by the current state of distant objects and so conforms to the Bell inequality. A more accurate criticism then is that hidden variable theories do not conform to special relativity.

The Kochen-Specker theorem further limits hidden variable theories. This states that in addition to being non local these theories must be contextual. Essentially, if properties of a quantum system are predetermined by unknown hidden variables then complementary properties can not appear to affect each other as the uncertainty principle requires. Therefore at least some properties must vary depending on the context of the measurement. Bohmian mechanics conforms to this limit by specifying only the particle position as determined. We will follow this example, and so the majority of quantum properties will need to emerge from the dynamics of our system.

The next issue that arises for these interpretations is that they are not testable. As Wallace puts it, these theories are underdetermined by empirical data. That is, whatever hidden variables exist cannot be measured since multiple configurations of hidden variables could lead to the same observed macroscopic state. Not only does such a theory not produce any testable prediction, it would not be possible to determine which hidden variable theory was correct as multiple models could produce the same predictions as standard quantum theory. This issue requires a model defined with more rigor than I have here.

Another challenge is that the dynamics of a hidden variable theory must produce the same statistical probabilities that the probabilistic standard model has established. Thus there must be some reason that the odds of various interactions are the same as measured. Either the dynamics of the model must converge to these probabilities or there must be an environmental factor, a universal state that forces the typical distribution. In this presentation we will not deal with specific probabilities, but dynamics with analogues to standard model interactions should at least seem to have similar probability.

Then there is the problem of what explains the quantum state. In Bohmian mechanics, the quantum state is represented by the guiding wave equation. This has led to criticism that the Bohmian interpretation is just many worlds with the extra step of picking out one possibility as real (i.e., claiming the particle is riding the 'real' wave). Other fluid interpretations are based on the Madelung equations, which reformulates Schrödinger's equation to terms similar to Navier-Stokes. Timothy Wallstrom showed that these formulations were not entirely equivalent, requiring what he called "ad hoc quantization" to recover Schrödinger. (T. C. Wallstrom, Phys. Rev. A 49, 1613 (1994)). So it is not clear what dynamic creates a quantum state in existing hidden variable theories.

Lastly, hidden variable theories are difficult to reconcile with quantum field theory. Wallace explains this by describing how QFT appears to treat particles as emergent (in that they are modeled the same way as quasi particles and their properties are scale dependent.). That is problematic for interpretations that require particle properties to be deterministic. Most hidden variable theories would treat particle position and number as definite, but these values depend on how a phenomenon was analyzed in QFT. Therefore an interpretation needs to account for this discrepancy. As mentioned in the introduction, we will deal with this by suggesting particles emerge from the dynamics of shockwaves.

In summary, our fluid model should meet the following requirements to supply an acceptable interpretation of quantum behavior:

1. The fluid model must allow any speed but somehow recover special relativity. We will modify this model to meet the requirement.
2. The model must define as few properties as possible and express quantum observables as emergent behavior. Since the fluid model describes particles as emergent, this should be met.
3. The dynamics of the model should in addition to replicating the standard model predict some other behavior that might be testable. I do not have the rigor yet to even reproduce existing predictions. However, I can point to explanations of confusing behavior of the standard model, and the explanation reinforces some speculation on quantum gravity.
4. The model should tend toward an equilibrium that produces observed probabilities. As I am still working on reproducing the interactions of the standard model, this work is incomplete.
5. It should be clear from the model what is quantized and how it produces the quantum state of the standard probabilistic model. We will discuss when we explore the dynamics of this model how the quantum state is produced.
6. As modern field theory represents particles as emergent, the fluid model should either also do so or explain how particle number is contextual. As in requirement 2, claiming that particles are emerging from shockwave interactions should meet this requirement.

A Super Simple Fluid Model

We will begin with Burgers' equation. Burgers' equation was first proposed as a toy model for turbulence in one dimension with very simple nonlinear advection and diffusion terms. With no viscosity the diffusion term disappears, and the resulting inviscid Burgers equation is considered a model for conservation equations. This is the model we will start with, and it takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0, u(x, 0) = f(x)$$

This system is usually analyzed with the method of characteristics. (For example in R. J. LeVeque's Numerical Methods for Conservation Laws (1992)) We can see that u represents a velocity. Any point x at time 0 will move by u as the system evolves, creating a linear characteristic line. If u decreases as x increases though, the characteristic lines will intersect at a future "breaking" time. After this point we must use weak solutions or else our solution would define multiple values of u at a single point. The correct weak solution for the system we are modeling matches additional conditions, usually called the entropy condition.

This is known as the Riemann Problem, which explores a discontinuity where u is u_l to the left and u_r to the right. For the Burgers' equation in the case where $u_l > u_r$ the solution fitting the entropy condition is a shockwave travelling at the average speed of u_l and u_r . We can see this conserves the total velocity of the system. In the case where $u_l < u_r$, the same shock wave is a valid weak solution but does not match the entropy condition. Instead, the correct solution is a rarefaction wave, where u_l and u_r move apart and produce a gradient between them. This also conserves the total velocity of the system. (Note that both waves move at the same speed, as the center of the rarefaction wave will move at the average of u_l and u_r .)

That is the standard discussion of Burgers' equation, and we can say this system conserves momentum. It does not, however, conserve kinetic energy. This is obvious if we imagine the characteristic lines are particles instead of fluid: the shockwave is clearly an inelastic collision. This loss of kinetic energy is known as anomalous dissipation. In most fluid models this is acceptable. Kinetic energy will convert into heat or some other form. In our case we want to model a fluid where other forces arise from emergent behavior. We cannot say the kinetic energy converts to heat, as that is velocity at a smaller scale and our model must work at the smallest scale. Similarly, other forms of energy rely on potential differences that cause a force to act. Therefore our fluid model must be something like a superfluid that conserves kinetic energy. So we must use a different weak solution, and not accept this entropy condition.

If the shockwave represents an inelastic collision, the rarefaction wave could represent an elastic one. Using a rarefaction wave does mean the function $u(x, t)$ must either be multivalued or discontinuous after the breaking time. But the shockwave already modeled a discontinuous u function. So in the case $u_l > u_r$ we can specify a discontinuity from u_l to u_r at x_l (the point where u is u_l), a velocity gradient from u_r to u_l (which will be discontinuous when created), and another discontinuity from u_r to u_l at x_r (the point where u is u_r). This creates a 'rarefaction' shockwave. To state that more precisely, when I write 'discontinuity from a to b ', I mean a jump discontinuity where the value at the discontinuity is b . Since x_l and x_r are the same point, this does mean we've defined two jump discontinuities and two values for the same point. These points must move apart though, so we can say instead that we are defining a new $f(x)$ an infinitesimal moment later when x_l and x_r have moved apart and the velocity gradient is no longer vertical. See the illustrations in figure 1 below.

Fig. 1. Rarefaction wave (left) and rarefaction shockwave (right) shortly after a discontinuity.

This is known as a rarefaction shock or an expansion shock, and they are known to be valid physical solutions in some rare cases. In most cases they are not considered physical because characteristic lines can converge into a shockwave but violate causality if they emerge from it. That is a problem here as well; consider what happens when two of these shockwaves meet. If two such rarefaction shockwaves overlap this function will truly become multivalued. In most cases though there is a simple solution: by the time these waves meet, the velocity gradient that caused the discontinuity is no longer discontinuous. We can therefore reverse the direction of the wave, removing both discontinuities and restoring a compression wave. This restores the velocity gradient to the original u_l to u_r . Since we are defining a new $f(x)$ at discontinuities and shockwaves will only meet when their leading points create a discontinuity, this is easily accomplished. I think this would be described as an unstable shock, and I believe it would not violate causality because the restoration of a compression wave means that the characteristic lines are not able to leave the neighborhood of the shock.

This suggests an algorithm for solving such systems. We can create an arbitrarily precise piecewise linear approximation for $f(x)$ defining linear velocity gradients. Each velocity gradient represents either a rarefaction wave, a compression wave, or a rarefaction shock. The breakpoints can be treated as the start and end of the wave. I will refer to them as shockpoints since they represent a discontinuity in the derivative of u and they can also represent discontinuities in a shockwave. We can evolve the system by evaluating only the shockpoints as the system evolves, and connecting them with linear gradients. As discontinuous gradients appear, the compression waves are replaced by shockwaves. If and when a neighboring gradient becomes discontinuous, a shockwave reverts back to a compression wave and we continue to evolve the system.

We can note here that even though we are conserving kinetic energy, we have created a mechanism for displacement that creates a kind of potential energy. This is accomplished by the discontinuities at shockpoints because points on one side will not move as their characteristic line would suggest. Instead they will be 'pushed' by the actual value of the shockpoint, and our algorithm keeps the value of u at that point even though it is displaced from the point it would be projected to reach.

This is illustrated in figure 2, created with a python simulation I wrote for the model. It shows the shockpoints of a compression wave with a neighboring rarefaction wave whose far shockpoint has a velocity of 0. When the compression wave becomes a shockwave the neighboring wave becomes a compression wave, and the shockwave expands until reaching the shockpoint at 0 velocity. At this point the shockwave again becomes a compression wave and the compression wave again becomes a rarefaction wave. In a sense, we have removed the shockwave by creating displacement. So you could describe the shockwave as a kind of potential energy. The system oscillates between an expanding shockwave that increases displacement and a contracting compression wave that reduces it. In a sense, we have defined a binary (one might even say quantum) harmonic oscillator. This suggests why I believe the model can reproduce quantum behavior. This shockwave dynamic can describe behavior like entanglement and other quantum states. It also provides the mechanism for protecting causality, as this reversion prevents the characteristic lines from leaving the area of the shock.

Fig. 2. Shockwave-compression wave oscillation in a python simulation.

You may have noticed that if the far shockpoint was approaching the oscillating wave, we would reach an undefined condition where three shockpoints and two waves are at a single point. What do we do when multiple waves end up at a single point? At that time, $f(x)$ will be continuous along x up to the shockpoint u_l . Here multiple discontinuous gradients exist, with shockpoints ranging from the highest valued shockpoint u_{max} to the lowest u_{min} . $f(x)$ will then be continuous from the shockpoint u_r and continuing on x . It is unclear if every shockpoint in the discontinuity must be tracked or if we can reduce the number of gradients to the minimum needed to track all values of u in the discontinuity. Since the argument is that interactions between shockwaves produce particles, and one of our constraints is that particle number can vary, for simplicity we will assume we do not need to track every velocity gradient (and therefore wave) but only every distinct value of u . Continuing to track every velocity gradient should be possible but more complex.

To accomplish this we will need to create linear velocity gradients connected by shockpoints in such a way that all distinct values of u are on at least one gradient and the value of the shockpoints are arranged in increasing order. Therefore they will separate as the system evolves. Since we are only preserving distinct values of u , if u_l and u_r span all distinct values only a single wave will emerge. If they don't, the shockpoints for u_{max} and u_{min} may require additional waves. So in our simpler model, a single point on x can contain up to 3 waves and 4 shockpoints. This generalizes our algorithm to cases where multiple waves exist at one point. I've illustrated several possible outcomes in figure 3.

Fig. 3. Various waves emerging from a discontinuity:

- (left) left higher than right plus max
- (middle) left lower than right plus max
- (right), left lower than right plus both max and min.

Note that there is some asymmetry in these graphs, which makes our plan 'remove the discontinuities' when a shockwave reverts unclear. We need more precise instruction: when a shockpoint containing a discontinuity reaches another shockpoint (creating a discontinuous gradient), we remove the discontinuity in those shockpoints by reverting them to their original value. The discontinuous shockpoints that were those values will instead become the value lost from the restored shockpoints. The function $f(x)$ is then defined by the revised shockpoints. This is effectively the same for the simple waves in figure 1, but allows us to address cases like in figure 3 where multiple waves exist at the same point. In the simpler cases both discontinuities are resolved whereas in the more complex cases there may still be discontinuities if not all the shockwaves emerging from a point have reverted.

Regarding the validity of this fluid model, I have not been able to find this kind of solution in existing literature. I am inexperienced with PDE systems, but I can not find a contradiction in this solution that would prevent it from being at least a reasonable approximation. As this is the fluid model we will explore, for this document I will simply postulate it is a valid model for approximating a superfluid.

I am going to refer to this as a Noether fluid model for a few reasons. Firstly, because Emmy Noether should have more things named after her. Secondly, because I believe this model preserves the same symmetries as the standard model that the Noether theorem predicts. That is, I suspect this model contains the same $U(1) \times SU(2) \times SU(3)$ symmetry as the standard model gauge group. Lastly and serendipitously, I call this a Noether fluid because the fluid this model describes is not Aether.

A Noether Sort of Relativity

Turning to our first constraint, the Noether fluid model should allow any speed but recover special relativity. Our model has not defined a maximum speed, but it does imply a universal coordinate system. In fact, when a shockwave reverts to a compression wave there is an instantaneous non local effect (in that the velocity or u value is instantly changed across the span of x between shockpoints). If we allow this instantaneous effect to occur across a universal t coordinate then we violate the principle of relativity. Since we want the model to have the same behavior regardless of frame of reference, we need to correct this.

Let's consider introducing frames of reference with a simple gauge invariance: we can reorient the x and t axes to make any value of $u = 0$. Regardless of how this changes the value of u , the difference between u_l and u_r in a wave (or velocity gradient) will be the same. This lets us introduce an orientation for x and t that varies based on local conditions.

Any point on x that is a shockpoint can be oriented to be stationary ($u = 0$). This gives us a relative u value for the other shockpoints from this shockpoint's reference frame. Any point on x that is in a wave and not a shockpoint can instead have the axes oriented to make the midpoint of the gradient stationary. Hence, the velocity of the wave will be 0 and each shockpoint of the wave will appear to be moving away or toward the center at the same speed. When a shockwave converts to a compression wave, it would occur along this axis. Hence from the wave or shockpoints' perspective the effect is instantaneous, but it may not appear so in other frames of reference. So we have a kind of universal t and x without a universal coordinate system, and no instantaneous effect extends beyond a local frame of reference. I believe this restores the principle of relativity. I suspect this also provides $U(1)$ symmetry, but I lack the expertise to show how.

This also serves to let us ignore the discontinuities at shockpoints. While the same point on x nominally has two values of u , reorienting the axes changes both values to 0. This will remain true regardless of how the values of u evolve, so that each shockpoint and wave continues to be stationary in its own reference frame. This means there are two methods to measure time elapsed for a shockpoint: either by the span of t in its current orientation or by simply measuring its length. For a wave time can be calculated from the length of its shockpoints, but the higher the velocity of the shockpoints the slower t of the wave will advance. If the shockpoints of a wave are moving infinitely fast, t will not advance at all. This leads us into the second postulate of special relativity, the speed of light.

The second postulate of special relativity is that the speed of light is the same in all reference frames. It is also often claimed that nothing can move faster than the speed of light. Since we have not yet defined photons we have not yet defined a light speed. Let us instead add a constraint to how photons can be defined: they must always appear to travel at the maximum possible speed. Now we only need to determine the maximum speed in our model. If it is not infinite and it is the same in any reference frame I think we satisfy this postulate. Since we have determined that within a wave universal time stops when the shockpoints move at infinite speed, let us try to calculate the velocity of $u = \infty$. Figure 4 is an illustration of a stationary shockpoint interacting with a shockpoint at infinite velocity.

Fig. 4. Shockwave interaction with shockpoints at u of 0 and infinity.

Note that t for this wave is oriented at 45 degrees, as determined by the average of the two shockpoints. We can see that from either shockpoints' perspective it is moving on average one x per one t . You might say that one lightsecond per second is the shock speed of a Noether fluid. We can see a sort of time dilation for shockpoints here as well. From either shockpoints' perspective, its current universal time only passes when it is stationary. When an interaction changes the frame of reference, the x and t axes flip and it instead sees its previous displacement as universal time passing, and its previous universal time as displacement where no time passes. So we have identified that $u = \infty$ can be compared to light speed. In this case, the shock travels at the shock speed, which is light speed, even though its velocity is infinite.

Alas, we must consider speeds in excess of infinity. Consider: as we orient the x and t axes to make $u = 0$, values of u will increase past infinity, becoming negative infinity (infinite velocity in the other direction) and back to 0. As this happens, that 'velocity' will appear to move faster and faster backwards in universal time. Luckily, as the velocity continues to 'increase' it actually moves slower. We can see this in figure 5, which shows shockwaves with one stationary shockpoint and one in excess of infinity. Notice that while the waves move faster than the shock speed, the 'faster' they move the more oscillations are required for movement. For a shockpoint therefore, the maximum change in x for traversed t is $u = \infty$. For waves, the fastest a wave can move in relation to its shockpoints is just less than $u = \infty$. Not only that, but the higher the potential energy of a wave (the larger the difference in velocity of its shockpoints) the slower time will advance for it.

Fig. 5. Shockwave interactions with shockpoints at u of 0 and in excess of infinity.

Notice also that while a shockpoint in a shockwave can trace a history moving backwards in its universal time, its total path still moves forward in universal time. From the point of view of a 'stationary' shockpoint, the shockwave it is part of moves from travelling left at infinite speed to travelling right, and universal time will then again advance in the shockwave in the same direction as the stationary shockpoint. This is because the universal time reverses direction for a shockwave orthogonally to the universal time of its shockpoints. That said, it should be possible for two separated waves to have their axes oriented in a way that they appear to each other to be moving backwards in universal time. Since we intend to show that the interactions of waves produce known particles, that means that a particle might appear to be evolving backwards in time. This is one colloquial description of antimatter. I will claim that this is how a Noether fluid reproduces antimatter. We could even claim that this is how the model shows CPT symmetry. Clearly a reversed universal time would necessitate a reversed parity. And since charges will arise out of the interactions of waves, it would make sense that reversing time and parity would in most cases also reverse charge.

While we've shown that moving backwards in universal time must be limited, figure 5 clearly shows events in the future affecting the past. Specifically the shockwave converting to a compression wave is caused by an interaction in the future that extends into the past. I would say this is the relativity of simultaneity predicted by special relativity. Within the wave those events are simultaneous. We could also claim this is analogous to other quantum mechanics interpretations that use retrocausality to resolve the measurement problem. These interpretations propose that future events can affect the past, and thus the wave function does not collapse but instead is constrained in some way by causal and retrocausal effects to be the unique observed value. I haven't delved into the merit of such interpretations, but it seems our model could be made to fit this mold.

Regardless, the retrocausal effects of a Noether fluid make it difficult to simulate. The first problem I dealt with was matching up 'universal' simulation times between points. It is simple to project the shockpoints along linear paths, and if a shockwave reverts we can project along the relative t axis to determine when the shockpoints update their u value. However, at least with my simulation logic there are frequent cases where a shockpoint reaches the same point as another shockpoint's historic path. Since faster moving shockpoints will move through universal time at a slower pace, this sort of synchronization issue is expected. In these cases we must rewind the simulation for that other point and any point it has interacted with before we can again project forward. Therefore each simulation step is evaluating shockpoints at a range of universal time, and keeping track of causal effects is difficult.

The more challenging issue is antimatter, or modeling shockpoints that appear to move backwards in time. (I don't have this working yet.) The approach I am trying is to specify an origin point for the x and t axes. The simulation then requires all shock points to be moving towards the origin and a specific distance from it. We can then create a polar coordinate where r (distance from origin) is simulation time and θ is x . Shockpart then arranges the shockpoints along x , creating a wave between each neighbor. Universal time can be counted as distance from the center of the simulation, and we start the simulation in negative time. In the first phase the simulation universal time will advance towards the center and when a shockpoint reaches its closest approach to the center, that shockpoint will no longer be in an x coordinate of the next step in universal time. Once the center of the simulation is reached, a second phase begins as universal time advances away from the center and is positive. When a shockpoint that has reached its closest approach is reached, its x coordinate will be in future steps of universal time. This will continue until all shockpoints reach the border of the simulation space.

This should allow us to take the end point of a simulation to run it in reverse and see no change in the final output. (As the simulator is a work in progress, this is not yet tested.) In theory, the simulation should produce the same results regardless of which direction we evaluate it. The intent is that in the second phase, any path from the first phase would appear to be an antiparticle. (Since I am certainly unqualified to speculate, I am not calling the second phase any kind of 'bang'.) Interestingly: while in planar coordinates we can see speeds of infinity, in polar coordinates infinity is tangential to x . This means a straight line connecting two points on x at the same t would in increasing simulation time appear at the midpoint and then move towards both points at 'light speed'.

Regardless, we appear to have a reasonable approximation of special relativity. With our first constraint satisfied, let us determine what features could be taken for standard model particles.

What are Z Bosons?

Perhaps the best way to start finding objects like standard model particles is to note that we have already declared one kind of exclusion principle: if we only model 4 shockpoints to a point, no more than 3 waves can exist in our model at the same point. Since the Pauli exclusion principle does not apply to bosons, it would make sense to declare bosons do not contain waves. Bosons must therefore be a shockpoint. Since a boson in the standard model is a force carrier this makes sense. After all, in a Noether fluid it is when shockpoints interact that things change.

This means that any number of bosons could exist at a single x coordinate. It might seem that the maximum would be defined by the waves, but consider that our model uses an arbitrarily precise piecewise approximation to define the shockpoints. This means that there could be any number of untracked shockpoints that our arbitrary was not precise enough to capture. We therefore should treat every distinct value of u in our function as a potential shockpoint. Thus an infinite number of shockpoints could exist at a single point of x if that point contains a discontinuity. (Although the number of shockpoints entering a discontinuity is not conserved. Our model preserves a minimum of one point for each distinct value of u .)

You could use a similar argument to claim that boson statistics apply to waves as well. After all, each of those infinite shockpoints is connected to two others by waves. But we might not track these waves in a discontinuity. If we track a maximum of four shockpoints in a singularity, our simple model does not preserve their connectedness. Therefore in our model shockpoints moving through a discontinuity would be preserved but the waves connecting them might not be, and new waves would instead be created connecting the shockpoints in a potentially different order.

We have pretty clear indicators that all bosons are shockpoints, but how do we differentiate them? Since we have not yet identified how electric or color charges emerge, we cannot yet identify W bosons or gluons. We certainly haven't identified the Higgs field yet. We cannot even claim these are photons, since we concluded that photons must always move at maximum speed and most shockpoints will not. For now then, we will refer to a generic shockpoint as a Z boson.

What About the Fermions?

Fermions are typically described as being modeled by spinors. Since we claim fermions are made up of waves, can we say a wave is equivalent to a spinor? At least an approximation of one, yes: the popular simplification of spinors is that they require 720 degrees to rotate and we can demonstrate that behavior. Take a wave made up of the shock points u_l and u_r . Since we are allowing speeds in excess of infinity to loop around, we can treat velocity as an angle and a change in velocity as rotation. We could imagine taking the u_r shockpoint and increasing its velocity a full rotation. Note that when we do so, u_r will pass u_l . This means the difference between their velocities will be in excess of 360 degrees which is not defined in our model - we have lost information. We could decide that this means that u_r is now on the other side of u_l , or we could simply declare this is not allowed in the model. Regardless of how we treat it, to recover the lost information we must rotate u_l until the difference in velocities is less than 360 degrees. Once we have done so, we have not returned to the original state until we complete a full rotation of u_l . Thus a wave must 'rotate' 720 degrees to return to its initial state. Obviously in higher spatial dimensions the direction of velocity would require the same kind of rotation.

Just like with bosons, we will define a default fermion that is as simple as possible: we will claim a single shockwave defines a neutrino. This gives us a neat way to explain why neutrinos rarely interact. When a neutrino interacts with a boson, it converts from a shockwave into a compression wave. That compression wave is indistinguishable from two separate bosons, so any further interaction could be interpreted as bosons interacting. The compression wave will eventually revert to a shockwave and the neutrino will again be noticeable.

Why couldn't we also describe the shockwave as two bosons? We first need to define the relationship that lets them affect each other at some distance. Luckily we have such a relationship in quantum mechanics. We can claim that a shockwave and therefore a neutrino describes two entangled bosons. Such an entangled state might seem too fragile: any interaction would destroy it. But note that a shockwave represents an oscillator, so the bosons would re-entangle after some time. Therefore the oscillation creates a robust pattern of entanglement.

If we call this entanglement, then clearly a shockwave reverting to a compression wave is a 'collapse' of a wavefunction. Indeed, the particle(or shockpoint) collapsing a shockwave has gained some specific information about the wave but it is incomplete. It might claim to know precisely where the wave was at a point in time, but since the wave was spread out at that point the knowledge loses accuracy as the wave shrinks to a point.

With repeated interactions, it might measure the frequency of oscillation and claim to know the energy of the wave, but that claim assumes knowledge of the wave's centerpoint. By measuring how the frequency changes, it can claim to know its velocity but again this provides no information about position. I don't think this can be resolved without information from the other side of the wave, and the collapse makes measuring both sides simultaneously a near impossibility. Nevermind that your information would cross multiple reference frames.

If this pattern represents entanglement, what could disrupt it? If a boson is moving towards a neutrino it will collapse the shockwave in shorter and shorter oscillations until they meet. When they meet there will be a discontinuity that two waves emerge from: thus we have gone from a one-wave neutrino to what we'll call a two-wave electron. We have thus identified a W boson. Since the only other bosons that interact with a neutrino are Z bosons, there must be a way for the entangled bosons of a neutrino to be disrupted that will not result in an electron. I can't picture this in the one spatial dimension I am simulating, but it might be possible in higher dimensions. If the boson that causes the shockwave to collapse is travelling faster than the boson in the neutrino, the new boson would entangle immediately with the boson in the neutrino, producing a new neutrino and an isolated boson that was part of the old neutrino. In one spatial dimension these particles will still meet, but it might be possible in higher dimensions for the new neutrino to miss the boson of the old neutrino, producing a neutrino with a different velocity.

Electrons: u Spins e Right Round

As we saw in figure 3, multiple wave shock configurations are asymmetric. If we define two waves in a point as an electron, we should expect the electromagnetic force to arise from that asymmetry. Indeed, we can see from figure 6 below that the electron wave will collapse differently depending on which side first began the collapse of the electron wave.

Fig. 6. An 'electron' consisting of 3 shockpoints between X 40 and 50, oscillating when reverted from a shock on the left (left) or right (right).

Figure 6 shows a two wave singularity like those described in figure 3. In this case, the left shock velocity is higher than the right shock, and the minimum velocity shock is in the middle.

When the shockwave is impacted on the left we can see:

- The left shock restores its velocity, passing its velocity to the right shock that had its velocity. This happens along a t axis aligned with the left and right shock.
- The left shock will then reach the middle shock, restoring its velocity. The right shock will be restored by the restoration of the middle shock along the t axis aligned with them. This is not shown because:
 - The middle shock will then impact the right shock before its velocity is restored. Since the right shock was then restored before the middle shock, we restore the velocity of the middle shock at an earlier point along the t axis of the middle and right shock. Since the middle and left shocks exchange velocity when impacting, this does not change the point that the right shock is impacted by the middle shock.

When the shockwave is impacted on the right we can see:

- The right shock restores its velocity, passing its velocity to the middle shock that had its velocity. This happens along the t axis that aligns with the middle and right shock (which had the velocity of the left shock). The middle shockpoint is not drawn to this point in the figure due to a bug in my simulation.
- The middle shock will then reach the right shock, causing it to restore its velocity. The left shock will have its velocity restored along the t axis that aligns with the middle and left shocks.

In both cases: further collapses have no effect on the point the electron converges to, as the oscillations on one side of the electron are symmetric and the centerpoint of the wave will not be changed by early collapses. Once the electron collapses to a point and the electron shockwave emerges it can again be influenced. The velocity of the centerpoint of this two wave oscillation is not affected by which side triggers the collapse, as far as I can tell. It is instead determined by the average velocity of the min and max shock before the collapse, and that velocity averaged with the right shock velocity after the collapse.

Next we can explore what dynamics could produce an electromagnetic force. I am not well versed in vector calculus, but electric charge is described as divergence and magnetic force is described as curl. While a neutrino is symmetric, the electron pattern is asymmetric in two ways. First, its shockwave is different from its compression wave. Second, there is left to right asymmetry, as in our example more extreme velocities are on the left and less extreme velocities are on the right. This provides clear analogues to divergence and curl. We can picture divergence as an asymmetry in time. The shockwave expands but cannot interact with anything, as it reverts to a compression wave when perturbed. Therefore an electron can only interact when it is converging to a point, so we could claim it has negative divergence.

Similarly, in the example electron the left two shocks are moving slower through time (are higher velocity) than the right. So we can see a sort of rotation similar to curl. If a velocity gradient can be the curl of magnetic force, then we should be able to model a magnetic field with an array of neutrinos with higher and lower energy. Figure 7 shows an attempt to reproduce the Stern-Gerlach experiment with neutrinos creating a magnetic field.

Fig. 7. The same electron as figure 6, surrounded by higher and lower energy neutrinos. The left graph is incomplete because my simulator enters an infinite loop before the simulation is finished.

These examples show the electron deviating from its path but there is insufficient detail to draw conclusions. The mechanism of deviation is clear though, which we can see occur in the first collapse of both pictures in figure 7. When this expanding electron is disturbed first on the right and then on the left, we see:

- As in the right picture in figure 6, the electron begins to collapse. Note that unlike the left side of figure 6, here the left shockpoint projects quite far to the left before internal dynamics revert it.
- When the left shockpoint is disturbed, it reverts to its velocity early. This results in the centerpoint of the left two shockpoints moving to the right, deflecting the electron to the right.

The same dynamic would occur in the opposite direction as well, but in the opposite direction (like the left side of figure 6) the opposite shockpoint that could be disturbed is actually moving faster towards the convergence point than it will when disturbed. That means not only is this interaction less likely to happen, but when it is perturbed on the right, the centerpoint will move some to the right. If it is perturbed early enough, it will shift the centerpoint of the two left shockpoints to the left as well. So statistically, such an interaction should be more rare and less predictable. I believe this means that if the side with the middle velocity in an electron is more likely to collapse first, it is statistically more likely to produce this deviation. Figure 7 does not have sufficient data to show this though.

This describes to us what spin is: the side of an electron with the lowest absolute velocity. If figure 7 had shown us the predicted result, we could have seen how that 'spin' would react differently in opposite magnetic fields. This also explains Fermi statistics. Even if we tracked all the shockpoints at a single point, there can only be one left shock and one right shock. Therefore, a single point can contain a spin left and a spin right electron. I could imagine additional electrons squeezed between the two electrons, but they would be encapsulated by the outer electrons, not visible and therefore not relevant.

However, I don't quite understand the spin of neutrinos. Neutrinos are only asymmetric in time, in that they also only interact after reverting to a compression wave. They are symmetric left to right and in terms of velocity, so they don't have spin in that sense. Even though the expansion and compression waves are the same shape there is still asymmetry so you could claim a kind of phantom electric charge but I don't know how that would appear to be spin. That said, in the same way that only two electrons can be visible from a single point, only two neutrinos would be visible within one point: the one on the right side and the one on the left side. Similarly, if the spin we measure is derived from the time asymmetry, we would measure all neutrinos to have the same spin, and all anti neutrinos to have the opposite spin, which is what experimentation shows.

On the other hand, it is easy to see how a positron would have a reversed charge. The positron moving backwards in time will appear to emerge from a point already oscillating until it suddenly becomes an uncollapsed positron wave. At that point it will shrink back into a point and no interactions will happen until that point is reached. The story of the electron will have played out in reverse, and the positron will appear to have the opposite charge of an electron. Note that not every two wave configuration will be an electron or a positron. If the three shockpoints that emerge from a point are not moving together they will simply be defined as a neutrino and a boson emerging from the same point and moving apart. So there are complexities to this picture that I have not explored.

What a Tangled Web

As you can see from figures 6 and 7, we have reached the limits of my ability to analyze the dynamics of this model. From this point on, I am forced to be more vague. I am not able to produce the behavior I expect in my simulations. I've gone through several iterations in working out these dynamics and in its current state my python simulator is prone to infinite loops and crashes. I've also introduced enough exceptions and special cases that even if it produced the expected results it could have been inadvertently tuned to produce the expected behavior. So while I have an idea for how this model can produce standard model behavior, I don't have clarity on how those dynamics work. Until I can experiment with a working simulation, I am not able to get that clarity. There are several points I am unclear on, but have ideas of how to resolve.

First: We've seen how fermion waves have something like a wave function but bosons which are shockpoints in this model have no such mechanism. I am not sure how to resolve this, but one possibility is to remember our shockpoints are an arbitrarily precise approximation. We can imagine a neutrino with a neighboring boson whose velocities are so close that they are effectively parallel. If these particles were sufficiently close, our model might approximate that 'electron' as a single shockpoint. As we evolve our system therefore we should expect our shockpoints to get fuzzier; our approximation becomes less and less accurate. Our simple model would therefore not capture the quantum properties of bosons, but we should expect to see that impact the accuracy of its predictions. Moreover, each shockpoint might represent a complex wave at a scale too small to model. (I am not sure if this is the same thing as a virtual particle.) If the wave is sufficiently complex it could produce the behavior predicted in the standard model, where a boson splits into two other particles while still conserving momentum.

This provides an alternate means of defining Z and W bosons: a Z boson would represent a neutrino, which when interacting with a neutrino would produce a symmetric wave of two 'neutrinos' (similar to the right image in figure 3). A W boson would represent an electron and therefore have a charge. Thus when interacting with a neutrino it could pass its third shockpoint to the neutrino turning it into an electron and itself into a Z boson. The current Noether fluid model as simulated is not able to distinguish between these two.

The second issue I haven't fully worked out is the Pauli exclusion principle. I have shown how spin is reproduced by the left most and right most shock at a point when creating a shockwave. We have also identified an exclusion principle as a sort of simplification, but in fact there does not seem to be anything preventing multiple fermions from occupying a single point. I suspect that the exclusion principle emerges from a kind of decoherence. That is, in cases where there are multiple 'particles' encapsulated between the left and right 'particles' of a point, the large-scale behavior of the point will be mostly defined by the left and right particles. However as additional shockpoints or particles are encapsulated the internal dynamics of collapsing to a compression wave will become more and more complex and take a longer and longer amount of time. I think at some point it will stop looking like only two particles and, akin to decoherence, begin to act as if the left and right particles are not entangled at all.

I do think there is an analogue for a kind of commutativity in this model that I think can describe how the Pauli exclusion principle describes. Noting again that our function is an arbitrarily precise piecewise function, we can imagine a discontinuity that at higher precision would not quite yet be discontinuous. If we modeled at higher precision then within the small range of this velocity gradient we could rearrange the position of almost any point in the model without changing the outcome our model predicts: once the points are discontinuous both precisions would still produce the same prediction. This is because when we have multiple shockpoints at a single point the model only tracks values of u that are in the discontinuity and does not preserve their finer position. There are two main exceptions to this: u_l and u_r .

Because these points are connected to points outside of the discontinuity, swapping these points with any other point in this range would change the outcome of the model. Of course these two points will always define at least one of the waves that emerges from the discontinuity, so we can say that in some sense the order of waves is important at every precision; they are not 'commutative'. So we have an admittedly tenuous connection between how our model handles shockpoints vs waves, and Bose-Einstein vs Fermi-Dirac statistics. There could be exceptions: If a configuration of waves representing particles can be enclosed in a larger wave that becomes a shockwave, then swapping the finer position of the waves would no longer impact the model. I am not sure if our model fully tracks this behavior, but I think it is required for this model to reproduce a Bose-Einstein condensate.

This is related to why we claim tracking only the extreme shockpoints (left, right, max, min) could be sufficient: These points describe the shape of the shockwave and compression wave. Any additional shockpoints could only have smaller (micro) effects on the larger (macro) wave. So we can argue that we only need the extreme shockpoints to model the behavior, because I believe the other shockpoints do not affect the simulation at a large scale.

In both of the issues I've discussed so far I've claimed a resolution is possible by considering multiple scales. I suspect that the Noether fluid model is scale invariant, but I do not have nearly enough experience in studying dynamics to determine if that is true.

Photons: Blinded by the Light

Much like the spin of neutrinos, I am unable to provide a clear picture for photons. If this model is correct we know that a photon is a boson: a single shockpoint that must always move at infinite velocity. I can picture three different ways to model this dynamic, and I am not sure which if any would describe a photon. I suspect a photon is a combination of these dynamics.

First, as I described when discussing modelling antimatter, a photon could be an artifact of converting polar coordinates to cartesian. All shockpoints travel in a straight line defined by their current value. If you are using polar coordinates, this means the speed of a shockpoint appears to vary. However, a shockpoint tangential to x would appear to start at a midpoint and travel at infinite speed. This could describe a photon and you could claim that time is not passing for it. This does not make the properties of light clear though, nor why a photon could pass through particles that cannot absorb it.

Second, the wavelength of a photon is described as an oscillation that is always parallel to its direction of travel. This is not possible in the one spatial dimension I am currently modelling. It is therefore possible that photons require more dimensions to fully understand. This would explain some properties of light, such as particles only being able absorb photons of specific frequencies. It does not explain why a photon must always travel at light speed or other properties of the photon.

Third, we know that a shockwave collapse happens instantaneously across a wave. It might be then that a photon is not a shockpoint, but a shockpoint equivalent of a soundwave. That is, a 'photon' might travel instantaneously across a shockwave when collapsed, and sit on the unperturbed side of the wave until that shockpoint is interacted with. If that shockpoint then collapses a neighboring shockwave, you could trace an instantaneously moving effect continuing to travel in that direction. You might be able to trace a sort of vibrational pattern of shockwave collapse that would alternatively be moving infinitely fast and not at all while waiting to collapse the next shockwave. This would explain the idea that a photon expands spherically until it is absorbed at only one point. This sort of dynamic is so complex I can barely picture it, let alone demonstrate it.

Putting Together a Higgs Mechanism

Since we have explored how a neutrino could turn into an electron and vice versa, as well as how the electromagnetic forces could arise, the only thing missing for electroweak unification is the Higgs mechanism. As it has been described, the Higgs field is a scalar field unlike other quantum fields. It also creates mass from a sort of drag effect when spin changes from one direction to the other. I don't fully understand the higgs mechanism, but I think I know approximately how it is paralleled in a Noether fluid.

If a shockwave appears to produce the quantum state, this suggests the cause of the higgs mechanism. We have treated the Noether fluid model as an approximation of a fluid velocity field. If I attempted to create a proper vector field for this model though, I would be limited in what starting conditions are possible because a velocity vector field does not capture existing shockwaves. In order to allow starting conditions to include shockwaves, one method we could use would be a scalar field that described existing entanglement of shockwaves. We've already described how this is a kind of potential energy, and potential energy according to other physics models produces mass as we expect the Higgs field to do. As I understand it, the velocity gauge field and a scalar entanglement measure field interacting to 'create' mass is similar to how the Higgs field works.

This also works for the 'drag' effect. We have already noted that an oscillating shockwave cannot reach infinite speed, at least in relation to its shockpoints. The spin of electrons and other particles, which represent additional waves, would have similar effects that you could describe as drag. I have not worked this out in detail, but the principle seems sound to me.

With this understanding I should be able to point out the SU(2) symmetry of the weak force. Sadly I am not certain what to point to. Since the weak force is a changing number of waves, my initial thought was that SU(2) symmetry is comparable to the symmetry between even and odd functions. If the difference between a W and Z boson is truly what they represent at a smaller scale though, it may be that the symmetry of the weak force arises from scale invariance.

Popping the Quarks

As mentioned, the original inspiration of this model was that quarks could be modeled as electrons with some fraction of their charge negated by the color force. Therefore the color force would be a component of momentum that was negated and so was not a part of the composite particle. Clearly, that is the effect of entanglement in a Noether fluid. Consider the velocity of a neutrino, which is the velocity of its component bosons that is not negated by the other boson. So one could describe two entangled electrons as having a shared momentum, and the 'lost' kinetic energy in the entanglement is a part of their momentum lost to a color force.

If you take this to be the color force then the three colors of the force would be the three dimensional components of momentum that were negated. In the one dimensional model I have been using there would only be one color to consider. We could still model a pion though, where a particle and an antiparticle entangle. Even in three dimensions, two such particles entangling would only cancel momentum along one specific axis so the analysis would be the same. As I haven't fully modelled this interaction the difference between two entangled electrons and two entangled quarks is not clear to me. Since we can model pions in one spatial dimension, in this arrangement at least it must involve entanglement along the t axis. Since in order for some of the charge of an electron to be negated one of the particles must be an antiparticle, this makes some sense.

A pion in this scenario then would be an electron and a positron entangled in some way. The electric charge of such a scenario would be unclear since the positron would only interact after the singularity point, and the electron would only interact before it. So the pion could be positive, negative or neutral depending on the relative size of the electron and positron. The 'larger' particle which is to say the particle with the longer interaction phase would dominate the dynamics and therefore determine the overall divergence. This describes for us how the up and down quarks are modelled in the Noether model. The larger of the two particles would be seen as an up or anti-up quark and the smaller would be seen as a down or anti-down. (This does mean that an up quark would be a positron.) If the two particles are the same size, then as in the neutral pion it would be unclear whether it was made of up or down quarks.

If this is a working model for quarks, then gluons would simply be shockpoints encapsulated inside the entanglement as we've discussed before. Indeed, these encapsulated waves would help explain the nature of the strong force. Adding energy is said to create additional quarks past a certain point. There is an analogue here between adding energy and changing the scale of our arbitrarily precise simulation. In both cases additional shockpoints that were encapsulated could become visible, making 'particles' or shockpoints that were previously too small to be detected become visible. Hence as you add energy additional quarks appear. As I have not really worked out the dynamics of what I'm describing I'm not sure if this can even happen in one dimension but I can see how it is possible.

I'm not entirely sure why three colors would be necessary when moving from two interacting particles to three, as in protons and neutrons. I think this is the same transition when moving from complex numbers to quaternions. That is, one imaginary number is sufficient but for more complex interactions you cannot use two but must move to three. Regardless, it would explain why a proton is more stable with an electron. Three particles will always make a plane, so there will be some asymmetry in the dynamics similar to vortex stretching where there will be positive divergence in one direction without a fourth particle to make a three dimensional structure.

In a similar way one could reason that a neutron would add symmetry along the t axis which would explain why atoms are more stable with neutrons. I suspect the vortex stretching analogy indicates why neutrons are unstable in isolation as well. I can't work out the details, but vortex stretching involves a vortex shrinking along the two dimensions of its rotation while growing in the third. This is clearly analogous to a compression wave. This means in a Noether fluid it would eventually turn into a rarefaction shockwave which shrinks in the third dimension. If this describes a neutron then it would of course be unstable, because as soon as it was perturbed it would revert to the stretching vortex of a compression wave.

Fermion: The Next Generations

So we have at least described analogues to the common particles of the standard model. We have not yet addressed the second or third generation fermions. This is difficult because the only difference with these particles is their mass, and we have barely discussed mass in this model. The only time we discussed mass was with the potential energy created by entanglement. So how could we postulate a higher mass version of emergent behavior of shockpoints?

This would be an excellent time to point out that we were able to describe the common fermions in only one spatial dimension. If we imagine the mass of a particle arising from the length of displacement in a shockwave then in higher dimensions the mass would be the area or volume. This would mean that a higher dimensional pattern similar to a fermion would have a mass increasing by orders of magnitude, which is approximately what we see in the second and third generation fermions.

But why would higher dimensional fermions be so rare? If this model is correct then I think it may actually be the case that they are not. I know that second and third generation fermions are rarely seen outside of particle accelerators, cosmic rays or radiation. In such situations the particle is moving at high velocity. If a fluid dynamic is moving at high speed through a medium it certainly makes sense that it would be unstable and prone to collapse in any direction not parallel to its motion. Thus such 'heavier' dynamics would appear unstable and collapse until the dynamic only occurred along the axis of motion. So if this model were correct we could claim that most electrons are actually tau but quickly collapse to an electron when perturbed.

Gravity Sucks

I've described how I picture the standard model arising from a Noether fluid. I had hoped to work out the dynamics in more detail but it is beyond my ability. Let us now turn to quantum gravity.

Researchers like Mark Van Raamsdonk have proposed that the spacetime of general relativity can arise from entanglement. I believe this can be supported by the Noether model. I think gravity arises from the aspect of Noether entanglement that is not in many models: the 'spooky action at a distance' of a far shockpoint of a shockwave reversing velocity. There are two ways I can think of to describe this, though of course I have again not worked out any specifics.

The first way is that a shockwave cannot be interacted with, or it reverts to a compression wave. Therefore along any given span or volume the entire space is not available for interaction. You could model this as the space shrinking or curving to describe only the space where interactions can happen. I believe this would be equivalent to claiming that entanglement acts as mass and curves space.

The other argument is simply that the dynamics of a Noether fluid produce an acceleration towards the densest area of shockpoints. Which is to say: when a shockwave reverts to a compression wave, it is more likely to do so in the places where shockpoints are the densest. This will result in shockpoints, on average, accelerating towards areas of higher density. Hence the unmodelled acceleration towards the shockpoint of a shockwave that was perturbed produces a gravity like effect.

Requirements for a Unified Model of Physics

If this model has any validity, it suggests that quantum field theory could be modelled with a single field instead of the current model which is a different field for each particle. Of course this theory is not worked out in detail and it could be that this model is only a useful metaphor. Even if this model is consistent it could be that it is missing details that require modelling multiple fields.

In conclusion, my results are inconclusive. I do not have the tools to take this work further despite my belief in it. I am not able to work out the full dynamics of this fluid model even in one dimension. What I have been able to work out does at least suggest that a pure fluid model can approximate quantum field theory. This would mean that the commonly disregarded hidden variable interpretations of fluid mechanics deserve further consideration. It does seem however that the criticism of Bohmian mechanics, that it arbitrarily selects a guiding wave by claiming a real particle rides the wavefront, has merit. We can instead claim that pure fluid dynamics can provide quantum dynamics. This is more in line with what I understand to be the most common interpretation of quantum physics: that particles do not exist and that the quantum fields are in fact the fundamental mechanism of physics.